

Translanguaging and Its Impact on Improving Reading Comprehension in Lesotho: Teachers' Perceptions

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Abstract

Original Research Article

This research examined the views of English teachers in Lesotho on the implementation of translanguaging as a teaching strategy to improve reading comprehension in learners. The study involved five purposefully and conveniently selected teachers from the Butha-Buthe and Quthing districts, employing a qualitative design that used semi-structured interviews to gather the teachers' experiences and insights. The findings indicated that teachers considered translanguaging to be an effective tool for scaffolding learning, enhancing comprehension, and validating learners' linguistic identities. Challenges such as the risk of overreliance on the first language (L1), inadequate teacher training, and misalignment with English-only assessments appeared to present significant barriers to implementation. The findings highlighted the necessity for professional development, policy reform, and resource allocation to effectively incorporate translanguaging into the educational practices of Lesotho. The study emphasises the significant potential of using learners' complete linguistic resources to mitigate ongoing challenges in reading comprehension and promote inclusive multilingual educational environments.

Keywords: Translanguaging, Reading Comprehension, Lesotho, First Language (L1), Second Language (L2), Pedagogical Strategies, Language Policy.

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INTRODUCTION

Historically, scholars have viewed languages as distinct and autonomous systems, leading to the common belief that the integration of a first language (L1) in second language (L2) instruction would impede the learning and proficiency of L2. The conventional pedagogical approach maintained the deliberate exclusion of L1 from L2 teaching methodologies (Qureshi & Aljanadbah, 2021). Critics often ascribe any relationship or overlap between the two languages to the inattentiveness of learners' language practices or the assumed deficiencies of teachers in English language proficiency. Maximilian Berlitz and other scholars advanced this understanding and promoted the direct method for teaching a second language (SL). Berlitz emphasised that acquiring a new language should reflect the process of L1 acquisition, wherein communication in the target language occurs naturally and inductively (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). His contributions were essential in advancing the Direct Method as a viable alternative to the traditional Grammar-

Translation Method.

In light of the current linguistic realities of multilingual societies, where the use of multiple languages is common, including within classroom environments (Qureshi & Aljanadbah, 2021), there has been a paradigm shift toward leveraging learners' existing linguistic resources. This approach, referred to as translanguaging, has gained prominence as a strategy for facilitating second language (L2) development (Ocampo, 2023). Advocates of translanguaging pedagogy emphasise its numerous benefits in L2 classrooms, highlighting their potential to affirm learners' identities, serve as scaffolding mechanisms, and function as a valuable resource for acquiring additional languages (Goli, 2023; Ledwaba, 2020; Makalela, 2015).

Translanguaging has emerged as a pivotal pedagogical strategy within multilingual education, offering a framework for leveraging learners' full linguistic repertoires to enhance educational outcomes. According to Makalela (2015) and Ocampo (2023), translanguaging is the active and deliberate use of more than one language in

the same communication or teaching situation. It has shown a lot of promise in improving language and cognitive development, especially in settings with a lot of different languages spoken. In the context of Lesotho, where linguistic plurality characterises both societal interactions and educational environments (Kolobe & Matsoso, 2020; Matee et al., 2023), translanguaging holds promise as a transformative approach to addressing persistent deficiencies in reading comprehension, a cornerstone of literacy and academic success.

Reading comprehension, an essential component of literacy, remains a significant challenge for learners in Lesotho. For the Secondary Education, there is persistent achievement gap across districts. Schools located in mountainous regions show poor performance compared to those located in the lowlands (Ministry of Education and Training [MOET], 2019). National assessment reports reveal consistently low performance in reading comprehension across various educational levels, with learners struggling to extract meaning, interpret ideas, and engage critically with texts in English, the medium of instruction in schools in Lesotho (MOET, 2020; Moea, 2024). This poor performance is often attributed to limited proficiency in English vocabulary, linguistic-geographical barriers, and inadequate pedagogical strategies that fail to bridge the gap between learners' first language (L1) and the second language (L2) (Lekhetho, 2013). These challenges are further compounded by resource constraints and the lack of teacher training in methods that support multilingual literacy development. Addressing these issues is critical, as reading comprehension is foundational not only for academic success but also for broader cognitive and social development.

The ability to comprehend texts is significantly influenced by learners' capacity to activate prior knowledge and employ diverse linguistic resources for meaning-making (Nur et al., 2020). By allowing learners to draw upon their L1 while engaging with L2, translanguaging facilitates deeper textual engagement and enhances cognitive processing (Goli, 2023). From the perspective of teachers, this pedagogical approach provides a robust framework for scaffolding learning, fostering inclusive classroom practices, and affirming learners' linguistic and cultural identities (Ledwaba, 2020). Despite its theoretical and practical merits, the integration of translanguaging into Lesotho's educational landscape remains inadequately explored, particularly regarding its perceived impact on learners' reading comprehension performance. This study aims to critically examine teachers' perceptions of translanguaging as a pedagogical tool for improving reading comprehension among learners in Lesotho. By situating these perceptions within the broader discourse on multilingual education, the research seeks to elucidate the potential of translanguaging to address the distinctive linguistic and educational challenges inherent to Lesotho's multilingual classrooms.

Literature Review

Linguistic Situation in Lesotho

Lesotho presents a unique linguistic landscape characterised by the coexistence of multiple languages,

being IsiXhosa, Ndebele, and IsiPhuthi, with Sesotho and English playing dominant roles. Sesotho, the national language, is spoken as a first language by the majority of the population and serves as a primary medium of communication in informal settings (Kolobe & Matsoso, 2020). English, on the other hand, holds official status and functions as the medium of instruction (MoI) from the upper primary level onwards, as well as the primary official language, business, and international communication (Moea, 2023; MOET, 2009). This diglossic situation creates distinct linguistic challenges, particularly within the educational system, where many learners are required to transition from using Sesotho and other minority languages at home and in early schooling to exclusively using English for academic purposes. Studies have shown that this shift often results in learners experiencing difficulties in comprehension and engagement, especially in subjects requiring advanced literacy skills (Kolobe & Matsoso, 2020; Matee et al., 2023). Furthermore, while Sesotho is highly integrated into cultural and social practices, its limited representation in formal education beyond the early years exacerbates the linguistic divide, contributing to poor literacy outcomes in English-medium instruction contexts (Makoa, 2023). This complex linguistic duality underscores the need for pedagogical approaches, such as translanguaging, that leverage learners' full linguistic repertoires to bridge the gap between these two languages and the minor ones and promote equitable learning opportunities.

Reading Comprehension and Multilingual Contexts

Reading comprehension is a fundamental aspect of literacy, encompassing the ability to decode, interpret, and critically engage with written texts. Scholars such as Snow (2002) and Perfetti and Stafura (2015) emphasise that effective reading comprehension relies not only on decoding skills but also on vocabulary knowledge, background understanding, and cognitive engagement. In multilingual contexts, learners' ability to comprehend texts is often mediated by their linguistic proficiency in both their first language and the second language. Cummins' (2000) interdependence hypothesis posits that cognitive and academic skills developed in L1 can transfer to L2, provided that learners are allowed to utilise their entire linguistic repertoire. This theoretical framework has significant implications for understanding reading comprehension challenges in multilingual societies such as Lesotho, where learners often face the dual burden of mastering academic content and language simultaneously. In Lesotho, poor reading comprehension performance among learners has been widely documented.

Studies have linked this trend to several factors, including inadequate exposure to English, insufficient vocabulary development, and a lack of effective pedagogical strategies tailored to the needs of multilingual learners (MOET, 2020, 2021). Furthermore, the rigid separation of L1 and L2 in classrooms has been identified as a barrier to meaningful learning, limiting learners' ability to draw on their linguistic resources to construct meaning and engage

critically with texts (Makalela, 2015). These findings underscore the urgent need for innovative and inclusive pedagogical approaches that address the unique linguistic challenges faced by learners in Lesotho.

Translanguaging as a Pedagogical Strategy

Translanguaging, defined as the purposeful use of learners' full linguistic repertoire to facilitate meaning-making and learning, has gained considerable attention as an effective strategy for multilingual classrooms (García & Li Wei, 2014). The approach challenges traditional monolingual norms by positioning multiple languages as complementary rather than competing resources in the learning process. Research suggests that translanguaging promotes cognitive engagement, enhances comprehension, and fosters critical thinking by allowing learners to access and integrate knowledge across languages (Canagarajah, 2011). In the context of reading comprehension, translanguaging enables learners to bridge gaps in understanding by using their L1 to scaffold their L2 learning. García (2009) and Makalela (2015) for instance, highlight that translanguaging supports vocabulary acquisition, contextualises unfamiliar concepts, and fosters a deeper understanding of texts. Moreover, this approach affirms learners' linguistic and cultural identities, creating an inclusive learning environment that validates their multilingual experiences (Lewis et al., 2012). These benefits are particularly relevant for contexts like Lesotho, where learners often face significant linguistic and educational barriers.

Teachers' Perceptions of Translanguaging

The success of translanguaging in classrooms heavily depends on teachers' perceptions and willingness to implement it as a pedagogical strategy. Teachers play a crucial role in shaping classroom practices since they are the implementers of curriculum, and their attitudes toward translanguaging significantly influence its effectiveness. Documented scholarship indicates that while some teachers recognise its benefits, others express concerns about its potential to hinder L2 development or disrupt traditional teaching norms (Mabena, 2023). In the African context, studies by Makalela (2015) and Maseko and Mkhize (2021) reveal mixed attitudes among teachers, with some viewing translanguaging as a necessary tool for addressing multilingual challenges, while others perceive it as an indication of linguistic deficiency. These divergent views underscore the importance of professional development and training to equip teachers with the skills and knowledge needed to implement translanguaging effectively.

In Lesotho, where the education system is predominantly English-medium, understanding teachers' perceptions is particularly critical for developing contextually relevant strategies to enhance reading comprehension and overall academic performance. In Lesotho, the hegemony of English is still maintained; English remains the medium of instruction from Grade 4 onwards (Moea, 2023). This way, the learner's identity, which is best reflected in their language, is divorced from the learners' knowledge acquisition. In its place, a monolingual system becomes

central. Learners' home languages are not perceived as a pedagogical tool that aids learning but as a hindrance or a problem to overcome (Mabena, 2023).

While the benefits of translanguaging have been extensively studied in global contexts, its specific application and impact in Lesotho's educational system remain underexplored. Existing literature focuses primarily on theoretical frameworks and generalised outcomes, with limited attention to teachers' perspectives, particularly in relation to reading comprehension. This gap is significant, as teachers' attitudes and practices are instrumental in determining the success of translanguaging as a pedagogical tool. By addressing this gap, the present study aims to provide nuanced insights into the role of translanguaging in enhancing reading comprehension performance and inform the development of more inclusive educational practices in Lesotho.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a qualitative research design to explore teachers' perceptions of translanguaging as a pedagogical strategy for enhancing reading comprehension among learners in Lesotho. The qualitative approach was deemed appropriate as it enables an in-depth exploration of participants' experiences, insights, and perspectives in their natural contexts (Creswell, 2013). Through the use of semi-structured interviews, the study sought to capture rich, descriptive data on the teachers' understanding, practices, and challenges related to translanguaging pedagogy. In this study, participants were purposively and conveniently selected. Five teachers of English were recruited from two districts in Lesotho: Butha-Buthe and Quthing. These districts were chosen to reflect a diverse representation of geographic and contextual factors influencing teaching practices in rural multilingual settings. Purposive selection was used to identify teachers with relevant experience in teaching English to multilingual learners, ensuring that their insights were directly aligned with the study's objectives. In the same vein, convenience selection facilitated accessibility and logistical feasibility, as the researcher prioritised participants who were available and willing to participate in the study. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, which provided a flexible yet focused framework for eliciting participants' perceptions and experiences. Key themes explored during the interviews included the use of translanguaging in teaching reading comprehension, its perceived benefits, challenges in implementation, and its alignment with assessment practices. With participants' consent, all interviews were audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed for analysis.

Results Analysis and Discussions

The findings from the study reveal a nuanced understanding of teachers' perceptions regarding the impact of translanguaging on learners' reading comprehension performance. The themes that emerged from the interviews highlight both the perceived benefits and challenges associated with integrating translanguaging pedagogy into classrooms in Lesotho.

1. Translanguaging as a Tool for Enhancing Comprehension

A majority of teachers expressed positive views about the use of translanguaging to facilitate reading comprehension, particularly for learners who struggle with understanding texts in English. Many teachers noted that allowing learners to draw on their first language (L1) during lessons enabled them to make connections between prior knowledge and new content. Teacher E stated:

“When I allow learners to discuss in Sesotho before answering in English, they seem more confident and their answers are more detailed. It helps them to first understand the question and think critically before responding.”

This aligns with existing research, suggesting that translanguaging enhances cognitive engagement and comprehension by leveraging learners’ linguistic resources (García & Li Wei, 2014). Teachers also emphasized that translanguaging serves as a scaffold, enabling learners to decode complex vocabulary and unfamiliar concepts.

Teachers noted that translanguaging aids in vocabulary acquisition, a key component of reading comprehension performance. Learners often grapple with understanding of texts due to unfamiliar terminology, but incorporating L1 as a scaffold helps clarify meanings. Teacher C reflected:

“Explaining new words in Sesotho before switching back to English allows learners to focus on understanding the text rather than being stuck on one word.”

This pedagogical practice highlights how translanguaging can serve as a cognitive tool that reduces linguistic obstacles, allowing learners to process and engage with texts more effectively hence improving performance.

Additionally, Teacher B remarked:

“Sometimes I translate difficult words or phrases into Sesotho, and it makes a huge difference. Learners grasp the meaning faster and can then focus on understanding the rest of the text.”

This practice reflects Canagarajah’s (2011) assertion that translanguaging supports meaning-making and facilitates vocabulary acquisition, which are critical for reading comprehension.

2. Affirming Learners’ Linguistic Identities

Several teachers highlighted the role of translanguaging in affirming learners’ linguistic and cultural identities, creating a more inclusive and supportive classroom environment. Teachers highlighted that learners often experience anxiety or a lack of confidence when required to engage solely in English, the medium of instruction. However, incorporating L1 into the classroom creates a sense of belonging and acceptance, which enhances participation and engagement. As Teacher A remarked:

“When I allow learners to answer in Sesotho during discussions of reading comprehension activities, they seem more comfortable sharing their thoughts. They feel like their voices matter.”

This sense of inclusion and affirmation has been widely documented in translanguaging literature, with researchers such as García and Li Wei (2014) emphasizing its potential

to empower learners by validating their multilingual identities. Teachers in this study also observed that learners who felt affirmed in their linguistic abilities were more willing to take risks and engage critically with texts. Additionally, teachers reported that translanguaging fosters a positive classroom dynamic by bridging cultural and linguistic gaps between learners. For instance, Teacher D noted:

“Using Sesotho in lessons helps me connect with the learners. They see that their language is valued, which builds trust and encourages them to participate more.”

This dynamic underscores the importance of translanguaging as not only a linguistic tool but also a means of fostering inclusivity and mutual respect within multilingual classrooms. Teacher B further shared:

“Many learners feel ashamed or afraid to speak in English because they think their English is not good enough. But when we use Sesotho in class, they feel included and participate more.”

This observation echoes findings from Makalela (2015), which emphasize the importance of validating learners’ linguistic identities to foster participation and engagement. Teachers noted that learners often perform better when their L1 is recognized as a valuable resource rather than a barrier.

3. Challenges in Implementing Translanguaging

Despite its perceived benefits, some teachers expressed concerns about the practical challenges of integrating translanguaging into their teaching. A recurring issue was the potential for overreliance on L1, which some feared might hinder learners’ proficiency in English. As teacher E explained:

“I worry that if learners rely too much on Sesotho, they might not improve their English skills, which are essential for exams and future opportunities.”

Teachers further expressed concerns about overreliance on L1, which they feared could impede learners’ development of English proficiency. The participants highlighted the need for balance, with Teacher A stating:

“While translanguaging is helpful, there is a risk that learners might depend too much on Sesotho and avoid practicing English.”

This reflects broader debates in the literature, where researchers such as Palmer et al. (2014) argue that translanguaging must be implemented strategically to ensure that L2 development is not compromised. Teachers in this study emphasized the importance of gradual transitions between L1 and L2 to build learners’ confidence in using English while maintaining comprehension.

Moreover, the lack of formal training on translanguaging pedagogy emerged as a significant challenge. Many teachers felt ill-equipped to integrate translanguaging effectively into their teaching practices. Teacher E explained:

“We need professional development workshops to help us understand how to use translanguaging in a structured way especially in cases where we have other ethnic groups despite Basotho learners.”

This underscores the necessity of equipping educators with the tools and strategies needed to maximize the benefits of translanguaging while addressing its potential drawbacks. This concern aligns with arguments in the literature suggesting that translanguaging must be implemented strategically to balance L1 and L2 use (Palmer et al., 2014). Additionally, teachers reported a lack of formal training on how to effectively use translanguaging in reading comprehension instruction. Teacher B noted:

"We were not trained to use other languages other than Sesotho in teaching, especially those who majored in Sesotho and English. Those who majored in English and other subjects may be going through a lot. Most of us are just figuring it out on our own, especially when meeting learners from Ndebele, Xhosa and Phuthi ethnicities."

This highlights the need for professional development programmes that equip teachers with practical strategies for translanguaging pedagogy, particularly in contexts where English remains the dominant medium of instruction.

4. Translanguaging and Assessment

Another theme that emerged was the tension between translanguaging practices and assessment requirements. Participants noted that while translanguaging enhances classroom learning, its impact on learners' performance in standardized tests remains unclear. Teacher D expressed:

"Examinations are in English, so even though learners understand the content through Sesotho, they might still struggle to express their answers in English."

This disconnect between instructional practices and assessment requirements reflects systemic barriers to implementing translanguaging effectively. Teachers emphasized the need for assessment reforms that accommodate multilingual strategies, ensuring alignment between classroom practices and evaluation criteria.

Another teacher emphasised the challenges in aligning translanguaging with English-only examinations, which often discourage the use of L1. Teacher A observed:

"In examinations, learners must answer in English, so surely using Sesotho in class will not help them perform better. It feels like we're working against the system."

This concern underscores systemic barriers to implementing translanguaging, as rigid language policies in assessment contexts can limit its effectiveness. Additionally, some teachers suggested that translanguaging could be integrated into formative assessments to support learners' comprehension and linguistic development. For example, Teacher C stated:

"If we include translanguaging in informal assessments, we can track learners' progress more accurately and identify areas where they need support."

This highlights the potential of translanguaging to transform not only classroom instruction but also assessment practices, paving the way for a more inclusive and equitable education system in Lesotho.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide important insights into teachers' perceptions of translanguaging as a

pedagogical tool for enhancing reading comprehension among learners in Lesotho. The discussion below situates these findings within the broader theoretical and empirical literature on multilingual education, highlighting both the practical implications and the challenges of implementing translanguaging pedagogy in this context.

Translanguaging as Comprehension enhancement tool

The data strongly suggest that translanguaging plays a pivotal role in fostering learners' understanding of reading texts, particularly in contexts where learners face significant linguistic barriers. By allowing learners to draw upon their first language (L1) to scaffold their understanding of second language (L2) texts, translanguaging aligns with Cummins' (2000) interdependence hypothesis, which emphasizes the transfer of cognitive and linguistic skills across languages. Teachers in this study observed that translanguaging not only aids in decoding complex vocabulary but also facilitates deeper comprehension by enabling learners to contextualize and internalize new information.

These findings resonate with prior research indicating that translanguaging supports learners' meaning-making processes (García & Li Wei, 2014; Canagarajah, 2011). By bridging the linguistic gap between L1 and L2, translanguaging mitigates the cognitive overload often experienced by learners in L2-dominant classrooms. However, the findings also highlight the need for a structured approach to translanguaging, ensuring that L1 use complements rather than replaces L2 engagement. This balance is crucial in enabling learners to develop the proficiency required for academic and professional success in English, the medium of instruction and assessment in Lesotho.

Affirming Learners' Linguistic Identities

The study underscores the importance of translanguaging in affirming learners' linguistic and cultural identities. Teachers noted that integrating L1 in classroom practices fosters a sense of inclusion, empowering learners who might otherwise feel marginalized in an English-only environment. This aligns with García and Li Wei's (2014) assertion that translanguaging validates the multilingual identities of learners, promoting confidence and active participation. The findings also highlight the role of translanguaging in creating a positive classroom dynamic. Teachers observed that learners were more likely to engage in discussions and share their perspectives when L1 was incorporated into lessons. This reflects the sociocultural benefits of translanguaging, which extend beyond linguistic outcomes to encompass social cohesion and mutual respect (Makalela, 2015). By valuing learners' linguistic backgrounds, teachers not only enhance their comprehension but also contribute to the development of a more inclusive and equitable educational environment.

Challenges in Implementing Translanguaging

Despite its benefits, the implementation of translanguaging in Lesotho's classrooms is fraught with challenges. Teachers expressed concerns about learners' potential overreliance on L1, which they feared might impede the development of English proficiency. This reflects broader debates in the literature, where critics of translanguaging caution against its unregulated use, emphasizing the need for strategic implementation (Palmer et al., 2014). The findings suggest that while translanguaging enhances comprehension, it must be carefully integrated into teaching practices to ensure that learners are continually exposed to and engaged with L2. Another significant challenge highlighted by the findings is the lack of formal training on translanguaging pedagogy. Teachers reported feeling ill-equipped to balance L1 and L2 use effectively, underscoring the need for professional development programs tailored to the multilingual realities of Lesotho. Such training would empower teachers to implement translanguaging strategically, maximizing its benefits while addressing its potential limitations.

Translanguaging and Assessment

The tension between translanguaging practices and English-only assessments emerged as a critical concern among teachers. While translanguaging facilitates classroom learning, its impact on learners' performance in standardized exams, which require English proficiency, remains uncertain. This misalignment reflects systemic barriers to the effective integration of translanguaging into educational practices. Teachers' concerns echo findings by García (2009), which highlight the constraints imposed by monolingual assessment policies in multilingual contexts. However, the findings also suggest opportunities for integrating translanguaging into formative assessments. By incorporating L1 into informal evaluations, teachers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of learners' progress and areas for improvement. This approach aligns with the principles of inclusive assessment, which prioritize the use of diverse strategies to capture learners' competencies (García, 2009). To address the challenges of standardized assessments, policymakers must consider reforms that accommodate multilingual practices, ensuring that translanguaging is not only supported in classrooms but also reflected in evaluation frameworks.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study explored teachers' perceptions of translanguaging as a pedagogical strategy for enhancing reading comprehension among learners in Lesotho. The findings indicate that teachers recognise the significant benefits of translanguaging, particularly its role in facilitating comprehension, affirming learners' linguistic identities, and fostering a more inclusive and engaging classroom environment. Translanguaging empowers learners by allowing them to draw on their full linguistic repertoire, thereby bridging the gap between their first language (L1) and second language (L2). However, the study also highlights practical and systemic challenges, including concerns about overreliance on L1, insufficient

teacher training, and the misalignment of translanguaging practices with English-only assessment frameworks. These findings underscore the need for a balanced and strategic approach to translanguaging, ensuring that it complements rather than detracts from the development of English proficiency. Moreover, the challenges identified point to the necessity of broader institutional support, including professional development and policy reforms, to maximise the potential of translanguaging in Lesotho's multilingual educational landscape.

To ensure the effective implementation of translanguaging, it is essential to provide teachers with targeted professional development programmes. These programmes should focus on practical strategies for integrating translanguaging into reading comprehension lessons, balancing L1 and L2 use, and scaffolding learners' understanding of complex texts. Workshops and training sessions should also address concerns about overreliance on L1 and emphasise how to strategically transition learners toward greater L2 proficiency. Educational policies and curricula should formally recognise translanguaging as a legitimate pedagogical approach. Curriculum guidelines should explicitly include translanguaging strategies, particularly in language and literacy education. Additionally, assessment policies should be reformed to accommodate the realities of multilingual classrooms. For instance, formative assessments could incorporate translanguaging practices to provide a more accurate measure of learners' comprehension and overall linguistic competence.

There is a need for the development of teaching and learning materials that support translanguaging pedagogy. Multilingual resources, such as bilingual glossaries, dual-language reading materials, and teacher guides, can facilitate the integration of L1 and L2 in reading comprehension instruction. These resources should be contextually relevant and aligned with the linguistic needs of learners in Lesotho. Schools should foster collaboration among teachers to share best practices and strategies for implementing translanguaging effectively. Peer-learning initiatives, such as teacher networks or communities of practice, can provide a platform for educators to exchange ideas, troubleshoot challenges, and build collective expertise in translanguaging pedagogy.

While this study provides valuable insights, further research is needed to explore the long-term impact of translanguaging on reading comprehension and overall academic performance. Future studies could examine how learners' proficiency in English evolves alongside the use of translanguaging and assess the outcomes of implementing translanguaging in other subject areas beyond language education. Translanguaging represents a transformative opportunity to enhance reading comprehension and create more inclusive educational practices in Lesotho. By addressing the challenges identified in this study and implementing the recommended strategies, educators and policymakers can unlock the full potential of learners' multilingual resources, fostering both linguistic and academic success in a linguistically diverse society.

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